

Complex formation equilibria of Fe^{III} with boric acid in presence of some aminopolycarboxylic acids

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Manuscript received 7 January 2003, accepted 14 October 2003

Equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of Fe^{III} with nitrilotriacetic acid and anthranilic acid diacetic acid (H₃L) in the absence and in the presence of boric acid in different molar ratios provide the evidence of formation of Fe(L)Fe(OH)⁻, Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻, Fe(L)(H₂BO₄)³⁻ and Fe₂(L)₂(BO₄)⁵⁻ complexes in solution. Stability constants of the complexes and the complex formation equilibria in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1° at a fixed ionic strength, I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) have been determined by potentiometric method.

Metal complexes of aminopolycarboxylate ligands have considerable biological relevance. Aminopolycarboxylic acids often serve as model ligands for mimicking metal-protein interactions *in vitro*¹. Some iron(III)-aminopolycarboxylate complexes have been found to serve as models for the active site of pyrocatalase² and induce tissue damage in rats in the presence of H₂O₂³. Ternary complexes of iron(III) ion having aminopolycarboxylate as one of the ligands have proven role in iron binding to transferrin⁴ and in strongly enhancing the antimicrobial action of ciprofloxacin⁵.

The present paper describes the results of the equilibrium study on the complex formation of Fe³⁺ ion with boric acid (H₃BO₃) in presence of two aminopolycarboxylic acid ligands viz., nitrilotriacetic acid (H₃nta) and anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid (H₃ada), hereafter, H₃L by potentiometric method.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria of the H₃L ligands (L = nta³⁻, ada³⁻):

Both the ligands H₃nta and H₃ada titrate as triprotic acids (H₃L) in the pH range 1.5–10. The first two steps of deprotonation occur almost simultaneously at lower pH values (pH ~2–3), whereas, the third and the final steps occur at higher pH values (pH ~7–10). Weakening of acidity of the -COOH group in the dianion, HL²⁻, may be due to its stabilization by intramolecular hydrogen bonding with

the two ionised carboxylate groups and the N-atom.

Fe^{III}-H₃L binary equilibria (L = nta³⁻, ada³⁻):

Major Fe^{III}-species in the binary Fe^{III}-H₃L systems at the early stages of the complex formation in aqueous solution (pH 2–3) are the ternary monohydroxo complexes, Fe(L)(OH)⁻, which with rise of pH are converted into the corresponding dihydroxo complexes, Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻, that constitute ≥ 90% of total Fe^{III} at pH ≥ 4.5. Binary Fe(L) complexes make only ~10% of total Fe^{III} at the beginning of the reactions (pH ≤ 2). Small amounts of Fe³⁺(aq), Fe(OH)²⁺ and Fe(OH)₂⁺ species are also identifiable in the speciation curves of the Fe^{III}-H₃nta system, but such species are negligibly small in the Fe^{III}-H₃ada system. Speciation of the 1 : 1 Fe^{III} : H₃L systems indicate the equilibria (2–8) in addition to equilibrium (1) for the formation of these Fe^{III}-L complexes :

Formation constants of the complexes, Fe(L), Fe(OH)²⁺, Fe(L)(OH)⁻ and Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻ can be obtained as computer output, from which the other relevant constants corresponding to equilibria (2–4) may be calculated according to the relations (2a–4a) :

$$\log K_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{H}} = \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{Fe}} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}} \quad (2a)$$

$$\log K_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{2\text{H}} = \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2}^{\text{Fe}} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}} \quad (3a)$$

$$\log K_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{H}} = \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2}^{\text{Fe}} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{Fe}} \quad (4a)$$

The overall formation constants of the complexes Fe(L), Fe(L)(OH)⁻ and Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻ may be defined according to the relations :

$$\beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}} = [\text{Fe(L)}] / ([\text{Fe}][\text{L}]) \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{Fe}} = ([\text{Fe(L)(OH)}][\text{H}]) / ([\text{Fe}][\text{L}]) \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2}^{\text{Fe}} = ([\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2][\text{H}]^2) / ([\text{Fe}][\text{L}]) \quad (11)$$

$\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}}$ values⁶ corresponding to the equilibria (7) and (8) may be defined according to the relations (7a) and (8a) respectively,

$$10^{(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_1} = \frac{([\text{Fe(L)(OH)}][\text{Fe}])}{([\text{Fe(L)}][\text{Fe(OH)}])} \quad (7a)$$

$$10^{(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_2} = \frac{([\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2][\text{Fe}])}{([\text{Fe(L)}][\text{Fe(OH)}_2])} \quad (8a)$$

$\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}}$ values characterise the coordination tendencies

of L³⁻ ligand ions to Fe(OH)²⁺ relative to Fe^{III}(aq) ion or the coordination tendency of OH⁻ ion to Fe(L) relative to Fe^{III}(aq) ions. Positive values, or values less negative than -0.6 of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}}$, indicate favoured formation of the ternary Fe(L)(OH)⁻ and Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻ complexes relative to Fe(L), Fe(OH)²⁺ and Fe(OH)₂⁺. $\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}}$ values for the equilibria (7) and (8) may be calculated using the relation (12–13) :

$$(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_1 = \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{Fe}} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{H}} \quad (12)$$

$$(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_2 = \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2}^{\text{Fe}} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}} - \log K_{\text{Fe}}^{2\text{H}} \quad (13)$$

which may be deduced from (7a) and (8a) on substitution from (9–11) and the appropriate of hydrolysis constants.

As the $\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}}$ values⁶ (Table 1) indicate, the monohydroxo ternary Fe(L)(OH)⁻ complexes are favourably formed with both nta³⁻ and ada³⁻. However the formation of the dihydroxo ternary complexes, Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻, is more favoured with nta³⁻, but much less favoured with ada³⁻. This is also evident from the speciation curves of the binary Fe^{III}-H₃L systems, which clearly show the formation of the ternary Fe(nda)(OH)₂²⁻ complex at much lower pH values than that is required for the formation of the Fe(ada)(OH)₂²⁻ complex. This may be due to higher stability of the binary Fe(ada) complex over the Fe(nda) complex, arising from to some sort of an involvement of the π -electron cloud of the aromatic ring system of ada³⁻ in metal ligand bonding.

Fe^{III}-H₃L-H₃BO₃ ternary equilibria (L = nta³⁻, ada³⁻) :

Complex formation equilibria involving Fe³⁺ and boric acid in presence of another ligand H₃L in aqueous solution

Table 1. Formation constants* of mixed ligand Fe^{III}-L-borate complexes with L = nta³⁻ and ada³⁻ in aqueous solution

I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃); temp. = 25°; $pK_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} = 9.00$

(a) Deprotonation constants of the ligands (H₃L) :

Ligands (L)	pK_1^{H}	Constants	
		pK_2^{H}	pK_3^{H}
nta ³⁻	1.98	2.45	9.76
ada ³⁻	1.65	3.11	7.59

(b) Fe^{III}-L binary constants :

Ligands (L)	$\log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}}^{\text{Fe}}$	$\log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}}^{\text{Fe}}$	Constants		
			$(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_1$	$\log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2}^{\text{Fe}}$	$(\Delta \log K_{\text{Fe}})_2$
nta ³⁻	12.48	11.02	+0.16	8.53	+0.33
ada ³⁻	14.42	13.21	+0.41	9.43	-0.71

$\log K_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{H}} = -1.62$, $\log K_{\text{Fe}}^{2\text{H}} = -4.28$

(c) Fe^{III}-L-H₃BO₃ ternary constants :

Ligands (L)	Constants						
	$\log \beta_{1112}$	$\log \beta_{2214}$	$\log K_{111}^{2\text{H}}$	$\log K_{111}^{\text{H}}$	$\log K_{221}^{5\text{H}}$	$\log K_{221}^{3\text{H}}$	$\log K_{221}^{\text{H}}$
nta ³⁻	17.03	31.34	-7.75	-0.50	9.86	11.32	13.81
ada ³⁻	18.28	34.83	-3.93	-0.15	11.41	12.62	16.40

*Limits of error in the constants : $\pm(0.02 \sim 0.05)$ in log unit.

may be described according to the general equilibrium (14) :
 $p\text{Fe}^{3+} + q\text{H}_3\text{L} + r\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^- \rightleftharpoons$

The overall formation constants (β_{pqrs}) of the mixed ligand borate complexes $[\text{M}_p(\text{L})_q(\text{H}_{(4-s)}\text{BO}_4)_r]^{(3p-3q-rs-r)+}$, may be defined as

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[\text{M}_p(\text{L})_q(\text{H}_{(4-s)}\text{BO}_4)_r]^{(3p-3q-rs-r)+} [\text{H}^+]^{(3q+rs)}}{[\text{M}^{3+}]^p [\text{H}_3\text{L}]^q [\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^-]^r} \quad (14a)$$

where p , q and r may be a positive integer or zero. s is the number of bound OH^- or the number of H^+ ion released due to the formation of a particular species. s is negative for protonated species, zero for neutral/normal species and positive for deprotonated or hydro species.

Mixed ligand complex formation in $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-H}_3\text{L}\text{-H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems have been studied using two different molar ratios of the reactants, viz., $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} : \text{H}_3\text{L} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 1 : 1 : 1$ and $2 : 2 : 1$. The predominant Fe^{III} species at the start of the reactions ($\text{pH} \leq 2$) in the $1 : 1 : 1$ $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} : \text{H}_3\text{nta} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ system (Fig. 1) are : $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{OH})^-$, (~40%); $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$, (~20%); $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})$, (~12%); Fe^{3+} , (~8%) and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ decrease steadily (eq. 1, 5, 7 and 8) and almost disappear at $\text{pH} \geq 3$. The concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{OH})^-$ increases slightly

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves for $\text{Fe}^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{nta} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 =$ (a) $1 : 1 : 1$ and (b) $2 : 2 : 1$ systems : (1) H_3BO_3 ; (2) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$; (3) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$; (4) $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})$; (5) $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{OH})^-$; (6) $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$; (7) $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^{3-}$; (8) $\text{Fe}_2(\text{nta})_2(\text{BO}_4)^{5-}$.

with rise of pH (eq. 2, 5 and 7) reaches a maximum (~45%) at $\text{pH} \sim 2.25$, then decreases steadily with rise of pH. Concentration of the dihydroxo ternary complex, $\text{Fe}(\text{nta})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$, however, increases steadily with rise of pH (eq. 3, 4, 6 and 8) reaches a maximum (~60%) at $\text{pH} \geq 3$, then decreases.

Due to higher stability of the Fe^{III} complexes with ada^{3-} relative to nta^{3-} , concentration of the $\text{Fe}^{3+}(\text{aq})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species are negligibly small in the $1 : 1 : 1$ as well as $2 : 2 : 1$ $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} : \text{H}_3\text{ada} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems (Fig. 2). Although such species are identifiable in the speciation curves of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-H}_3\text{nta}\text{-H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems (Fig. 1), these are practically nonexistent in the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-H}_3\text{ada}\text{-H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems (Fig. 2). The only binary Fe^{III} species at the start of the reactions in the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-H}_3\text{ada}\text{-H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems is the $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})$ complex, which with rise of pH is converted into $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})(\text{OH})^-$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ complexes in successive steps (eq. 2-4).

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for $\text{Fe}^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{ada} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 =$ (a) $1 : 1 : 1$ and (b) $2 : 2 : 1$ systems : (1) H_3BO_3 ; (2) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$; (3) $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$; (4) $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})$; (5) $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})(\text{OH})^-$; (6) $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$; (7) $\text{Fe}(\text{ada})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^{3-}$; (8) $\text{Fe}_2(\text{ada})_2(\text{BO}_4)^{5-}$.

In the $2 : 2 : 1$ $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} : \text{H}_3\text{L} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ systems, the binuclear complexes, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)^{5-}$ are the major Fe^{III} species right from the beginning of the reactions ($\text{pH} \sim 2$). Concentrations of these complexes increase steadily with the rise of pH. Around $\text{pH} \geq 4$ these binuclear complexes constitute almost 100% of total Fe^{III} [i.e., ~50% as $\text{Fe}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)^{5-}$].

As the speciation curves imply, the mixed ligand borate complexes, Fe(L)(H₂BO₄)³⁻ and Fe₂(L)₂(BO₄)⁵⁻ are formed by the reaction of H₃BO₃ with Fe(L), Fe(L)(OH)⁻ and Fe(L)(OH)₂²⁻ according to equilibria (15–19) :

Formation constants (β_{1112} and β_{2214}) of the mononuclear and binuclear mixed ligand borate complexes, Fe^{III}(L)(H₂BO₄)³⁻ and Fe₂(L)₂(BO₄)⁵⁻ respectively, may be defined according to

$$\beta_{1112} = \frac{[\text{Fe(L)(H}_2\text{BO}_4)] [\text{H}]^2}{[\text{Fe}][\text{L}][\text{B(OH)}_4]} \quad (20a)$$

$$\beta_{2214} = \frac{[\text{Fe}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)] [\text{H}]^4}{([\text{Fe}]^2 [\text{L}]^2 [\text{B(OH)}_4])} \quad (21a)$$

for which the ligand species B(OH)₄⁻ may be derived from ionisation equilibrium of H₃BO₃ in aqueous solution according to

$$K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{B(OH)}_4^-]}{[\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3]} \quad (22a)$$

The constants β_{1112} and β_{2214} may be obtained as computer output, from which the equilibrium constants of the reactions (15–19) may be calculated using the relations (15a–19a) respectively.

$$\log K_{111}^{2\text{H}} = \log \beta_{1112} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}^-}^{\text{Fe}} + \log K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} \quad (15a)$$

$$\log K_{111}^{\text{H}} = \log \beta_{1112} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2^{2-}}^{\text{Fe}} + \log K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} \quad (16a)$$

$$\log K_{221}^{5\text{H}} = \log \beta_{2214} - 2\log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)}^-}^{\text{Fe}} + \log K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} \quad (17a)$$

$$\log K_{221}^{3\text{H}} = \log \beta_{2214} - 2\log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}^-}^{\text{Fe}} + \log K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} \quad (18a)$$

$$\log K_{221}^{\text{H}} = \log \beta_{2214} - \log \beta_{\text{Fe(L)(OH)}_2^{2-}}^{\text{Fe}} + \log K_{\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3}^{\text{H}} \quad (19a)$$

Because of the very high formation constants due to hard-hard interactions, the Fe^{III}(nta) and Fe^{III}(ada) complexes are formed at sufficiently low pH solutions. As both nta³⁻ and ada³⁻ act as (O⁻, O⁻, O⁻, N) quadridentate ligands, these Fe^{III}-complexes are coordinately unsaturated and exist in aqueous solution as their diaqua-, monoquamonohydroxo- or dihydroxo forms, [(L)Fe(H₂O)₂], [(L)Fe(OH)(H₂O)]⁻ and [(L)Fe(OH)₂]²⁻ respectively. As the nta³⁻ and ada³⁻ ligands can not coordinate all the four equatorial positions in an octahedral geometry, the H₂O and the OH⁻ ligands in these (L)Fe^{III}-complexes are coordinated *cis*- to each other, although Fe^{III} in these complexes is substitution labile. Therefore, complex formation of H₃BO₃ with these Fe^{III}-L complexes (L = nta³⁻, ada³⁻) may take place in much the same manner as with the substitution inert [(L)Cr^{III}(H₂O)₂] complexes⁷, leading to the formation of (L)Fe(H₂BO₄)³⁻ and (L)Fe(BO₄)Fe(L)⁵⁻ complexes with enhancement of acidity of H₃BO₃ solution.

Experimental

Boric acid, nitrilotriacetic acid, sodium nitrate, nitric acid were of A.R. grade. Anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid was synthesised by condensing anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) with monochloroacetic acid (0.022 mol) following the process as described in literature⁸. Fe(NO₃)₃ solution was prepared and standardised as described earlier⁹.

Equilibrium study involved pH-metric titrations in aqueous medium of a series of solutions (25 ml) containing known amounts (0.0005–0.001 *M*) of H₃BO₃ and/or H₃L (L = nta³⁻, ada³⁻) and known amount (0.01 *M*) of free HNO₃, in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.0005–0.001 *M*) of Fe^{III}-nitrate, keeping the Fe^{III} : H₃L : H₃BO₃ ratios 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 with carbonate free¹⁰ standard 0.1 *M* NaOH solution at a fixed temperature of 25° maintaining a fixed ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 *M* (NaNO₃) following the same procedure as described earlier¹¹.

Ionic product of water at the experimental temperature and the activity coefficient of H⁺ ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from the literature¹². Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion corresponding to the pH meter readings were obtained by the usual procedure¹³. Formation constants (Table 1) were calculated with the aid of the SCOGS computer program¹⁴. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of the species distribution curves (Figs. 1,2) obtained as computer output.

Acknowledgement

Authors grateful thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of SRF to Ansuman Das and to the U.G.C. for

the award of JRF to Susmita Bandyopadhyay.

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